

Recent Advancements In Bioanalytical Method Development

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ABSTRACT

Bioanalytics involves the analysis of drugs, metabolites and biomarkers in biological matrices such as blood, plasma, urine and serum. In pharmaceutical research, bioanalytical methods are crucial for studying pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, bioequivalence, and drug-drug interactions. Method validation ensures the accuracy, sensitivity, selectivity, reproducibility, and reliability of analytical results. Traditional techniques like UV spectroscopy, HPLC, and GC have limitations in terms of sensitivity and matrix interference. Therefore, modern bioanalysis has turned toward sophisticated hyphenated techniques like LC-MS/MS, uhplc-ms, and hrms, which provide faster analysis and higher sensitivity. Recent developments in sample preparation include microextraction, electromembrane extraction, and dried spot techniques, which have improved effectiveness and lowered solvent and sample consumption. This review summarizes recent developments in modern bioanalytical sample preparation techniques and their applications in pharmaceutical research.

Keywords: Bioanalytical methods Sample preparation; LC-MS/MS; Microextraction techniques.

INTRODUCTION

The word “Bioanalytics” refers to the study of the requested analyte in biological fluids. The bioanalytical techniques are essential in the present pharmaceutical industry for the quantitative determination of macromolecules and low molecular weight medication molecules. The quantitative determination leads to the evaluation and interpretation of pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, drug drug interaction, bioequivalence and compatibility studies. Validation of any analytical method ensures that the developed method is reproducible, stable, sensitive, robust, appropriate, and reliable for its applications in blood, plasma, urine, serum, and faeces analysis.[1]

Earlier, development of bioanalytical systems mainly relied on conventional techniques such as fluorimetry, ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy, gas chromatography, and high-performance liquid chromatography. These methods were beneficial but had limitations including longer analysis time, lower sensitivity, poor selectivity, reduced perceptivity, and

difficulty in analyzing complex or low-concentration drugs.[2]

In Current bioanalytical procedures, a robust sample Preparation and modern instrument methods are Required. It also Includes selection, processing conditions, testing, Standardization, data evaluation, and reporting.

Modern pharmaceutical analysis has moved towards advanced and hyphenated approaches. Methods such as LC– MS/MS, UHPLC–MS, GC–MS, high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and ion-mobility MS provide much higher sensitivity, better selectivity, and faster analysis. These recent technologies can detect very small quantities of drugs and metabolites with great accuracy and meet the strict requirements of regulatory agencies like FDA and ICH.[3]

In addition, more bioanalytical studies have been reported on liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and solid-phase extraction (SPE). Recently, dispersive liquid-

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liquid microextraction (DLLME) and electromembrane extraction (EME) have become more acceptable due to their advantages in clinical investigations. Therefore, continuous improvement of novel sample preparation and microfluidics-based techniques is necessary to accelerate bioanalytical research. In the present article, we review the current publications associated with sample preparation techniques in bioanalytics. This article does not intend to be inclusive but rather intends to address the principles, advantages and disadvantages, and capability for practice in bioanalytical laboratories based on the authors' collective knowledge and experiences. Therefore, recent advances in chromatographic and mass-spectrometric technologies have made bioanalytical methods more reliable, robust, and suitable for today's complex drug development processes.[4]

Method Development :

Bioanalytical method development is the process of making a Procedure to unknown compound or novel compound be identified And measured in a matrix. A compound can often be measured by Several methods and the choice of analytical method involves, that is, Chemical properties of the analyte, concentrations, sample matrix, cost Of the analysis method and instruments, speed and time of the analysis, Quantitative or qualitative measurement, precision and necessary Equipment. Method development includes sample preparation Sampling, separation, detection and evaluation of the results and final conclusion.[5]

Previous Bioanalytical Techniques :

Earlier bioanalytical analysis mainly relied on conventional techniques such as UV-Visible spectrophotometry, HPLC with UV or PDA detection, gas chromatography and thin layer chromatography. These techniques were simple and cost-effective and were widely used for bulk drugs and dosage forms; however, they showed limited sensitivity and selectivity when applied to complex biological matrices due to matrix interferences.

Conventional immunoassays such as radioimmunoassay (RIA) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) were also employed

for quantitative analysis, but they suffered from cross-reactivity and limited specificity. Due to these limitations, conventional bioanalytical techniques were gradually replaced by advanced and hyphenated techniques to meet regulatory and sensitivity requirements.[6][7]

Limitation :

- Low sensitivity
- Poor selectivity
- High sample volume requirement
- Longer analysis time
- High matrix interference

Need Of Modern Bioanalytical Method

Complexity of the Sample: Because biological samples are intricate matrices, proper sample preparation Is essential for precise and trustworthy results.

- **Specificity and Sensitivity:** Detecting and measuring analytes at low concentrations requires the Development of techniques with high sensitivity and specificity.
- **Automation and Miniaturization:** Creating automated and miniature bioanalytical platforms can save Expenses and increase throughput.
- **Integration of Bioanalytical Techniques:** A more thorough understanding of biological systems can be Obtained by combining several bioanalytical techniques.
- **New Technologies:** Aptamers, DNA walkers, and nanobiosensors are becoming more and more Promising instruments for bioanalytical[8][9]

Modern Sample Preparation Techniques In Bioanalytics :

Currently, the increasing demand for convenient and eco-friendly sample preparation techniques is indisputable. Solvent extraction methods, including

LLE, liquid-phase microextraction (LPME), and associated perspectives, such as solid-liquid extraction (SLE), are ideal for bioanalytics. Such techniques lower the cost of drug development and yield interest in pharmaceutical manufacturing.[10] High sample throughput can be accomplished when automation is carried out, ensuring increased accuracy and low waste generation of harmful materials.

Recent studies have focused on the evolution of sample preparation techniques to achieve these benefits. The cybernation of extraction methods (e.g., SPE, LPME, and LLE) and other sample preparation methods using robotics has led to novel and elegant perceptions of bioanalytics.[11]

1. Microextraction Techniques

With the efforts of researchers, non-exhaustive microextraction techniques have developed appreciably in terms of sensitivity and accuracy from complex biological matrices. Microextraction techniques are based on the principle of using low volumes of solvents. Microextraction techniques are robust, versatile, solvent-free, and cost-effective. Automation of several microextraction techniques is appropriate for regular laboratory analyses. The primary microextraction techniques developed over the past decade are as follows:

- **DLLME (Dispersive Liquid-Liquid Microextraction)**

In 2006,[12] Berijani et al. introduced DLLME as a new alternative for bioanalytics. DLLME has several advantages, including simple operation, minimum sample volume, cost-effectiveness with high recovery, quick processing, and no necessity for any particular appliance. The drawback is the exercise of harmful halogenated solvents, including carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, and chlorobenzene.

To reduce the use of harmful solvents in extraction, newer trends in DLLME have recently been developed, namely, binary solvent (BS)-DLLME, air-assisted DLLME, and vortex-assisted LLME, the last of which resembles the solidification of floating organic droplets (DLLME-SFO). DLLME can also be applied for the simultaneous determination of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, meropenem, linezolid,

and piperacillin in human plasma sample BSDLLME has been reported for the quantification of tramadol in urine samples. In DLLMESFO, a high-density waterimmiscible solvent (e.g., dodecanol and 2-dodecanol) was used as the extractant. It has been used to determine orthophosphate, . The additional benefits, disadvantages, and applications of DLLME-SFO are similar to those of DLLME. Recently, ILs have been acknowledged as a potential choice for traditional DLLME techniques because of the exclusive properties shown by ILs from an environmental point of view, such as high thermal stability, nominal vapor pressure, and low flammability[13]

- **Thin Film Microextraction (TFME)**

TFME is a technique developed to address the limiting uptake rate in fiber microextraction. Because of its suitability for integrated sample preparation, it was introduced as an alternative to SPME. The major advantage of TFME is that it reduces sample handling with lower detection limits for the desired analytes. TFME mainly facilitates fast extraction kinetics and high extractive capacity. Recently, two eco-friendly approaches relying on TFME for water examination were submitted to interlaboratory validation using the US-EPA method-8270.[14] In this technique, analytes are extracted in a thin film of adsorbent material (e.g., graphene oxide) deposited on a solid support[15]

- **EME (Electromembrane Extraction)**

EME is a microextraction strategy based on mass transfer across an SLM. EME was introduced to reduce the extraction time. Primarily, the extraction depends on electrokinetic migration in an electrical field. EME is mainly convenient for the extraction of basic analytes with high polarity. EME can remove either cations or anions and has been verified as a valuable fractionation method for charged metabolite complex matrices. Currently, EME is mostly applied to moderately lipophilic ionized compounds, such as organic ions, from various matrices. Drouin et al. [16] investigated cardiovascular biomarkers and hydrophilic analytes in plasma. Alternatively, EME has been applied to nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as diclofenac, salicylic acid, ketorolac, ketoprofen, and tetracyclines in plasma

Recently, aristolochic acid and antipsychotic drugs (e.g., risperidone, chlorprothixene, and haloperidol)

were separated in whole blood and urine and analyzed by electromembrane extraction-liquid chromatography tandem-mass spectrometry (EME-LC-MS/MS) [17]. Mainstream pharmaceuticals are basic or acidic in nature, and therefore can be easily studied by EME.

Other Microextraction Techniques

Other microextraction techniques such as air-assisted liquid-liquid microextraction (AALLME)[18], single-drop microextraction (SDME), thin-film microextraction (TFME), and solid-phase nanoextraction (SPNE) [19] have also been explored for the extraction of analytes from biological matrices. These methods offer advantages such as reduced solvent consumption and simplified extraction procedures. However, limitations related to drop instability, limited robustness, complex sorbent preparation, and restricted applicability in routine pharmaceutical bioanalysis have confined their use mainly to research-oriented or niche applications.

2. Microsample Preparation

Microsample preparation techniques involve sample preparation of small sample volumes (<50 μL) of biological fluids. They can improve animal welfare, that is, smaller numbers of animals are required in studies due to the reduction in the volume of biological matrices. Microsample preparation aligns with the 3R (reducing, reusing, and recycling) benefit strategy in nonclinical studies. Apart from this, microsample preparation possesses business considerations such as minimal inventory in animal husbandry, sample storage, shipment, and analysis [20].

- **Dried Blood Spot (DBS)**

In 1963, Guthrie and Susi [21] introduced DBS to monitor the inborn metabolism defects in neonates. DBS is based on the principle of adsorption of biological components on the surface of a membrane carrier, followed by drying. Recently, DBS has gained wide attention in bioanalytical and clinical laboratories. DBS resembles metabolomics

examination, providing a dominant tool for studying new biomarkers and facilitating therapeutic drug monitoring [22]. DBS samples are easy to collect, store, and convey to places other than whole blood, serum, or plasma. DBS benefits clinical trial studies by reducing blood sample preparation volume. DBS has a considerable optimistic impact on accuracy and data quality in animal studies.

- **Dried Plasma Spot (DPS)**

Similar to DBS, DPS is a new emerging technique for the early diagnosis of neurodegenerative disorders. The DPS is a unique two-filter-paper-based remote blood collection tool. It offers numerous benefits compared to conventional plasma collection methods. Dried spot collection on filter paper is easy, has no requirement for refrigeration, and can be transported with the least biohazard risk. These benefits offer significant flexibility to DPSs with respect to the classical methods of sample preparation. DPS has been used to determine fosfomycin, ritonavir, trimethoprim, and sulfamethoxazole in biological matrices. Recently, DPS was shown to be suitable for the determination of amikacin, lithium and caffeine in biological matrices. DPS has proven to be a prominent technique when applied to PK studies, where plasma sample preparation is rapid and requires negligible plasma volumes [23,24].

- **Microdialysis**

Microdialysis is a well-known method that is usually useful in regular bioanalytical research, where a probe with a tiny semipermeable membrane is positioned in the desired tissue. Microdialysis not only restricts dull sample preparation and cleaning protocols in bioanalysis, but also permits concurrent sampling at several sites with rapid and simple operation. Microdialysis has been used to collect macromolecule-free samples in complex biological matrices. Currently, microdialysis possesses an extensive ability for in vivo investigations. It is capable of real-time analysis, but the analysis is restricted to polar molecules. [25]

3. Sorbent-Based Microextraction Techniques

Currently, for the development of supramolecular microextraction SPME fibers (ILs) immuno-sorbents

(ISs), metal nanoparticles (NPs), mesoporous-nanoporous silicates, carbo-nanomaterials, MIPs, electrospun fibers, and MOFs have become a hot research field and will be discussed. The main sample preparation methods include SPME as mentioned earlier, pressurized liquid extraction microextraction by packed sorbent MIPs carbon nanomaterials integrated MIPs, monolith spin extraction turbulent flow chromatography, salting-out liquid-liquid extraction (SALLE), and stir bar sportive extraction (SBSE).[26]

- **Restricted Access Materials (RAMs)**

RAMs permit the clean-up of biological fluids through physicochemical diffusion barriers. RAMs are composed of a porous material with a restrictive and hydrophilic outer surface RAMs permit repetitive injection of complex biological matrices. RAMs have been used for the rapid analysis of pyrethroids in whole urine samples RAMs are named as 'intelligent' sorbents due to their ability to retain analytes and exclude macromolecules.[27]

- **Microextraction By Packed Sorbent (MEPS)**

Nowadays, MEPS is a popular miniaturized sample preparation technique in bioanalysis that adheres to the advantages such as automated, simple operation, and cost-effectiveness. In general, MEPS consists of four stages such as sample loading with washing, elution, and sorbent post-cleaning. In MEPS, the solvent volume used for the elution of the analytes is small (10–50 μ L). Recently, MEPS has been applied in the determination of zonisamide, meropenem, levofloxacin, statins, and fluoxetine in plasma. In addition, MEPS is also beneficial for the determination of beta-blocker, mandelic acid, antidepressants, and asthma biomarkers in urine as well as psychoactive drugs, lamotrigine, and local anesthetics in saliva samples They have been applied to the resolution of organic and inorganic analytes from various biological matrices [28]

4. Other Promising Bioanalytical Sample Preparation Techniques

Some recent developments with the advantages of well-known bioanalytical sample preparation techniques are briefly described here.

- **Biofluid Sampling (BFS)**

BFS has proven to be a novel technique for the investigation of whole blood samples. BFS is capable of whole blood sampling without converting it into plasma or serum. A sampler can hold a whole blood sample of 10– 1000 μ L. In contrast, BFS shares operational principles similar to DBS with the abolition of technical drawbacks. BFS offers a novel and extremely simplified approach for whole blood sample preparation. It is expected to renovate the existing practice of blood investigations. BFS has been used to determine ketoprofen, carprofen, and diclofenac in human whole blood [29]

- **Aptamers**

- Recently, aptamers have gained significant attention in scientific research. Aptamers are chemical oligonucleotides that bind to specific target molecules. Aptamers have gained substantial attention as molecular detection elements in the clinical field, therapeutics, and bioanalytics. Aptamers have been adapted for the selective extraction of cocaine and tetracyclines in biological fluids and antibiotics in food matrices. Recently, aptamers have been used as surface drug nanocarriers in anticancer therapy, and their clinical and bioanalytical applications are growing rapidly.[30]

- **Hyphenated And Chromatography Techniques :**

Recent advances in bioanalytical method development have been largely driven by the emergence of hyphenated and advanced chromatographic techniques. Hyphenated techniques involve the coupling of an efficient separation method, such as liquid or gas chromatography, with a highly sensitive detection system, most commonly mass spectrometry, to enhance analytical selectivity and sensitivity. Among these, liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–

MS/MS) has become the gold-standard techniques for the quantitative analysis of drugs, metabolites, and biomarkers in complex biological matrices such as plasma, serum, urine, and whole blood. LC–MS/MS offers excellent sensitivity, wide linear dynamic range, and high reproducibility, making it highly suitable for pharmacokinetic, bioavailability, bioequivalence, and therapeutic drug monitoring studies.

Recent chromatographic advancements, including ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with MS/MS (UHPLC–MS/MS), have further improved analytical throughput by reducing run time, solvent consumption, and sample volume while maintaining high resolution. High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) provides accurate mass measurements and is increasingly employed for metabolite identification, impurity profiling, and non-targeted bioanalysis. In addition, other hyphenated techniques such as gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS), ion mobility–mass spectrometry (IM–MS), and two-dimensional liquid chromatography (2D-LC) are utilized for specific bioanalytical applications involving volatile compounds or highly complex biological matrices. Overall, hyphenated chromatographic techniques play a crucial role in modern bioanalysis by meeting stringent regulatory requirements and enabling reliable analysis of trace-level analytes.

- speeding up the analysis and less analysis time.
- accuracy in measurement.
- precise results.
- better reproducibility.
- analysis of low concentration of analyte(s).
- elucidation of complex structure.
- separation and quantification can be achieved.
- higher degree of automation.
- sophisticated sampling and further analysis

1.LC-MS/MS((Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry)

Liquid Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) is a powerful Analytical technique that combines the separation capabilities of liquid chromatography with the mass Analysis precision of tandem mass spectrometry. LC–MS/MS offers high sensitivity, allowing for the detection of compounds at trace levels. Additionally, the Technique is versatile, capable of analyzing a wide range of compounds, from small molecules to large Biomolecules. The ability to quantify and identify substances with high accuracy and precision has made LC–MS/MS a cornerstone in bioanalytical research, particularly in pharmaceutical development and clinical Studies. [31]

2.UHPLC-MS/MS(Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry)

Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC–MS/MS) is an advanced bioanalytical hyphenated technique that couples ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) with tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS). It provides high separation efficiency, rapid analysis, enhanced sensitivity and selectivity compared to conventional HPLC–MS. UHPLC uses sub-2 μm particle columns and high pressure to achieve faster run times and better peak resolution, while MS/MS enables specific multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for accurate quantification in complex biological matrices.

In clinical and pharmacokinetic studies, UHPLC–MS/MS is widely used for therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM), quantification of drugs and metabolites, and distinguishing closely related compounds with high specificity and precision. The method outperforms immunoassays and older techniques in sensitivity and ability to detect active metabolites.[32][33]

3.LC-HRMS (Liquid Chromatography–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry)

Liquid Chromatography–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC–HRMS) is a powerful bioanalytical hyphenated technique combining high performance liquid chromatography (LC) with high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) for separation

and detection of analytes. LC–HRMS provides accurate mass measurement, enabling identification of unknown compounds, metabolites, and impurities in complex biological samples with high sensitivity and selectivity. It supports both targeted and non-targeted analysis and is widely used in pharmacokinetics, metabolomics, toxicology, drug discovery, and quality control studies. LC–HRMS allows retrospective data analysis and high-throughput screening due to full-scan acquisition modes and advanced data processing. [34]

Challenges In Bioanalytical Techniques :

the rapid advancements in bioanalytical methods, several persistent and emerging Challenges hinder the accuracy, reliability, and scalability of these techniques, especially in Pharmacokinetic (PK) and toxicokinetic (TK) studies. These challenges span technical Limitations, regulatory complexities, biological variability, and economic constraints.

• Sensitivity And Specificity At Low Concentrations

One of the core difficulties in bioanalysis is the detection and quantification of trace-level Analytes in complex biological matrices Like plasma, urine, or tissues. Drug metabolites or Degradation products are often present in extremely low concentrations, Sometimes in Picograms or even femtograms per milliliter. Inadequate sensitivity or non-specific signal Interference from Endogenous substances can result in false positives or underestimation of Analytes, impacting study reliability.

• Matrix Effects And Sample Complexity

Biological matrices contain a mixture of proteins, lipids, salts, and other compounds that can interfere with the analytical signal. This phenomenon, commonly known as matrix effect, leads to ion suppression or enhancement, especially in mass spectrometrybased techniques. Even with proper sample clean-up and internal standards, complete elimination of matrix interferences is often difficult, leading to variability in results across different samples or populations. Stability of Analytes Certain drug compounds and their metabolites are chemically unstable under storage or processing conditions.

Analyte degradation may occur due to exposure to heat, light, or enzymatic activity, which can lead to erroneous PK or TK interpretation. Ensuring sample integrity through proper storage, stabilization techniques, and immediate processing remains a critical challenge, especially in multi-center or global studies.

• Regulatory And Validation Complexity

Global regulatory agencies such as FDA, EMA, and CDSCO mandate rigorous validation of bioanalytical methods for accuracy, precision, linearity, robustness, and reproducibility. Meeting these requirements across different countries and study protocols increases documentation burden and operational complexity. The need for cross-validation, partial validation, and revalidation in case of method modifications further adds to the regulatory workload.

• Cost And Instrumentation Constraints

Modern techniques like LC-MS/MS, high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and Capillary electrophoresis require costly instrumentation, specialized consumables, and trained Personnel. Smaller pharmaceutical companies, academic labs, or institutions in developing Countries may lack access to such resources, leading to reliance on outdated or less sensitive Methods.

• Ethical And Logistical Barriers In Sample Collection

Collecting biological samples for PK and TK studies from special populations like neonates, Geriatrics, or endangered animals poses ethical and logistical challenges. For example, Repeated blood draws may not be feasible, and some analytes degrade quickly post-collection. Furthermore, international transport of biological specimens often encounters legal, Biohazard, and customs regulations.

• Data Handling And Integration

With automation and high-throughput methods, bioanalytical studies generate large datasets. Efficient data processing, storage, integration, and interpretation require advanced Bioinformatics tools and regulatory compliant software. Ensuring data

integrity, traceability, And audit-readiness across the analytical pipeline is an increasing challenge, especially under Good Laboratory Practices (GLP). [35] [36]

Application For Recent Bioanalytical Methods :

- **Pharmacokinetic (PK) Studies.**

Modern bioanalytical methods are used to measure drug concentrations in biological samples at different time intervals. These data help in determining pharmacokinetic parameters such as C_{max}, T_{max}, AUC, and half-life.

- **Bioavailability And Bioequivalence (BA/BE) Studies.**

Bioanalytical methods are applied to compare the rate and extent of drug absorption between test and reference formulations. These studies are essential for generic drug approval.

- **Clinical Trials.**

During clinical trials, validated bioanalytical methods are used for accurate quantification of drugs and their metabolites in biological matrices. This ensures data reliability and patient safety.

- **Metabolite Identification.**

These methods are used to identify and quantify drug metabolites formed after administration. This helps in understanding drug metabolism and safety profile.

- **Therapeutic Drug Monitoring (TDM)**

Modern bioanalytical methods help in monitoring plasma drug levels of drugs with a narrow therapeutic index to optimize dosage and prevent toxicity. [37][38][39]

CONCLUSION :

Recent advancements in bioanalytical science have significantly transformed pharmaceutical and clinical analysis. The shift from conventional analytical techniques to modern hyphenated instruments has improved sensitivity, selectivity, and regulatory compliance. Along with instrumental progress,

innovative sample preparation techniques such as microextraction, electromembrane extraction, cloud point extraction, and dried spot methodologies have played a crucial role in handling complex biological matrices. These techniques miniferences..

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